

AUDIT QUALITY AND FINANCIAL STATEMENT QUALITY OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Audit Quality, Audit Independence, Audit Fees, Audit Expertise, Audit Tenure, Financial Reporting Quality, Tertiary Institutions, Nigeria.

Abstract: *The study investigated the influence of audit quality on the financial statement quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The specific objective were the effects of audit independence, audit fees, audit expertise, and audit tenure on the quality of financial reporting among tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria, with emphasis on the relevance and timeliness dimensions of reporting quality. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design and covered a population of fifteen (15) public and private tertiary small population size; a census sampling approach was employed. Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to finance, accounting, internal audit, and management personnel of the institutions. The collected data were analysed using univariate, bivariate, and multivariate statistical techniques. The findings revealed that audit independence, audit fees, audit expertise, and audit tenure each have a positive and statistically significant effect on the relevance and timeliness of financial reporting quality. Specifically, institutions with more independent auditors, adequate audit remuneration, higher levels of auditor competence, and appropriate auditor tenure demonstrated improved reporting practices characterized by greater decision usefulness and timely disclosure of financial information. The study concludes that audit quality attributes play a critical role in enhancing financial reporting quality within tertiary institutions. The findings provide empirical evidence supporting the strengthening of audit governance mechanisms to improve accountability, transparency, and stakeholder confidence in higher education institutions. The study recommends policies aimed at safeguarding auditor independence, investing in auditor capacity development, ensuring adequate audit funding, and establishing balanced auditor tenure frameworks to sustain high-quality financial reporting.*

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Introduction

Financial reporting quality (FRQ) remains a fundamental issue in accounting, auditing, and public sector governance because it determines the credibility, transparency, and usefulness of financial information provided to stakeholders. High-quality financial reporting facilitates informed decision-making, strengthens accountability, reduces information asymmetry, and enhances public confidence in institutional governance (IPSAS, 2023). FRQ is rooted in the qualitative attributes of useful financial information established by the International Accounting Standards Board. According to IASB (2018), financial reports are considered high quality when they exhibit the fundamental characteristics of relevance and faithful representation, supported by enhancing characteristics such as comparability, verifiability, timeliness, and understandability. Consequently, FRQ reflects the degree to which financial statements accurately portray the economic reality of an entity and meet the information needs of stakeholders. In public sector institutions, particularly tertiary institutions, financial reports serve as important accountability instruments through which governments, regulatory agencies, funding bodies, and the public evaluate the stewardship and utilization of public resources. Consequently, the credibility and usefulness of

financial statements largely depend on the quality of auditing processes that verify and validate reported financial information. The International Public Sector Accounting Standards Board (2023) emphasizes that high-quality financial reporting enhances transparency and enables stakeholders to evaluate how public resources have been acquired, managed, and utilized.

Globally, concerns regarding financial misstatements, accounting irregularities, and governance failures have increased scholarly attention on factors influencing financial reporting quality. Major corporate failures, including Enron, Worldcom, and Parmalat, highlighted the critical role of auditing in ensuring the credibility of financial reports and preventing financial misrepresentation (Francis, 2024). FRQ has become a major global concern due to its critical role in promoting transparency, accountability, and confidence in financial markets and public institutions. High-quality financial reporting enables stakeholders to make informed decisions by providing reliable and relevant information about an entity's financial performance and position. However, recurring incidents of financial misstatements, earnings manipulation, accounting fraud, and corporate failures have raised persistent concerns regarding the credibility and integrity of financial reporting globally (Francis, 2024). These developments shifted attention toward audit quality as a key determinant of FRQ,

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resulting in extensive empirical and theoretical investigations into how audit mechanisms influence reporting outcomes. Audit quality is generally defined as the probability that an auditor will both detect material misstatements and report them appropriately (DeAngelo, 1981). The concept encompasses auditor independence, competence, professional skepticism, audit evidence, audit tenure, audit fees, and audit firm characteristics (Francis, 2024). High quality audit enhances the credibility of financial statements by reducing managerial opportunism, constraining earnings manipulation, and improving compliance with accounting standards. Consequently, audit quality is widely regarded as a critical governance mechanism for improving FRQ and strengthening stakeholder confidence in financial disclosures.

In the public sector, the importance of audit quality has increased significantly due to growing demands for transparency, accountability, and efficient resource management. Public institutions are entrusted with substantial public resources and are expected to demonstrate stewardship through transparent financial reporting. Consequently, the quality of financial reports has become a critical indicator of governance effectiveness and institutional accountability (IPSAS, 2023). This concern is particularly relevant in developing economies where weak institutional frameworks, inadequate oversight mechanisms, and

governance challenges often undermine financial reporting credibility. In Nigeria, public sector financial reporting has undergone significant reforms following the adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS). The transition to IPSAS was intended to improve transparency, comparability, reliability, and accountability (Ademola et al, 2020). Nevertheless, concerns regarding reporting delays, weak internal controls, inadequate disclosures, and financial irregularities continue to challenge the quality of financial reporting in many Nigerian public sector entities (Nwanyanwu, 2017). The relevance of audit quality is particularly pronounced in tertiary institutions because these institutions manage substantial public funds derived from government allocations, internally generated revenue, research grants, donor funding, and intervention programmes. Universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education are expected to maintain high standards of accountability due to the strategic role they play in national development and human capital formation. However, increasing concerns regarding financial mismanagement, weak oversight structures, and reporting deficiencies have intensified calls for stronger audit systems capable of enhancing FRQ within tertiary institutions (Zibaghafa & Chukwu, 2024).

Recent empirical evidence from Nigeria provides substantial support for the argument that audit

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quality significantly influences FRQ across both private and public sector organisations. For instance, Nwaunaynwu (2017) found that audit quality practices, including auditor independence and compliance with auditing standards, significantly improve the reliability and credibility of financial reports in Nigerian organisations. Similarly, Ogungbade et al (2021) reported that audit quality attributes positively influence FRQ among listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, suggesting that effective auditing enhances the integrity of financial disclosures. Consistent with these findings, Wobo et al (2024) observed that audit quality mechanisms contribute significantly to improved FRQ through enhanced monitoring and reduced reporting irregularities. Evidence from the Nigerian public sector also supports the relevance of auditing in promoting accountability and transparency. Agwor and Amangala (2020) found that audit evidence significantly improves financial statement quality in government owned companies in Rivers State, indicating that rigorous audit procedures strengthen the reliability of financial information. Similarly, Adekanmi et al (2024) reported that audit attributes such as auditor competence, independence, and professional diligence positively influence perceptions of FRQ among Nigerian firms. These findings suggest that audit quality remains a critical determinant of credible financial reporting irrespective of organizational context. Studies focusing

specifically on tertiary institutions have also highlighted continuing concerns regarding financial accountability and reporting practices. Zibaghafa and Chukwu (2024) observed that compliance with public sector accounting standards significantly improves FRQ in higher institutions located in Rivers and Bayelsa States. Their findings suggest that institutional commitment to accounting standards and effective audit oversight are essential for achieving credible financial reporting outcomes. Despite these contributions, empirical evidence investigating the direct link between audit quality and FRQ within tertiary institutions remains limited, particularly in Rivers State. This gap underscores the need to further investigate into how audit quality dimensions influence the completeness, neutrality and timeliness of financial reports in public tertiary institutions. This study contributes to the growing literature on public sector auditing and provides evidence relevant to policymakers, regulators, and institutional administrators seeking to strengthen accountability and governance within tertiary educational institutions.

Statement of the Problem

Tertiary institutions are vital to society because they tackle a range of humanitarian, social, and environmental issues but to keep the public's confidence and get funds, they must guarantee accountability and openness in their financial reporting procedures (Zibaghafa & Chukwu, 2024). The quality of audits conducted on higher

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institutions become paramount. Appah and Zibaghafa (2023) noted that financial reporting of non-profit making organizations is often characterized by unique complexities, including diverse revenue streams, compliance requirements, and stakeholders' expectations. Despite these complexities, there is a growing concern regarding the quality and reliability of financial information presented by higher institutions in Rivers State. Donatella (2022) opines of effectiveness of audits in ensuring the accuracy and transparency of financial reporting in these organizations as central challenge. Yamen and Can (2023) argue that the traditional measures of audit quality may not fully capture the unique aspects of non-profit organizations, such as their reliance on volunteer resources and diverse funding sources which reveals lack of consensus on audit quality metrics. The scholars further noted absence of standardized metrics to assess audit quality specifically within the context of non-profit organizations as one obviously identified problem in the study concerned. While audit quality is typically evaluated based on factors such as auditor's independence, competence, and objectivity, the applicability of these metrics to non-profits remains unclear. Although audit quality is presumed to influence the reliability and credibility of financial reports, empirical evidence on this relationship, particularly within the higher institutions, is sparse. While some studies suggest a positive relationship between

audit quality and financial reporting quality (Asogba et al, 2024; Muhammad, 2024; Olalere & Adegbe, 2023; Putri et al, 2024; Yamen & Can, 2024; Donatella, 2022), others find mixed results or even indicate potential adverse effects (Gebreyesus, 2022; Yeng & Oppong, 2024; Wobo et al, 2024). This lack of consensus underscores the need for further investigation into the specific mechanisms through which audit quality affects financial reporting outcomes in higher institutions. Studies highlights the challenges faced by higher institutions in overseeing the audit process and suggests that these challenges may compromise audit quality and financial reporting integrity, this brings to bear the challenge of non-regulatory compliance and governance in audit reporting in the sector being investigated. Nevertheless, while existing literatures provide valuable insights into audit quality and financial reporting in the higher institutions, several knowledge gaps persist, indicating the need for further research: Limited focus on higher institutions-specific audit quality metrics; understanding that prior studies often rely on generic measures of audit quality, overlooking the unique characteristics and challenges faced by higher institutions. More so, inconsistent empirical findings: The empirical evidence on the relationship between audit quality and financial reporting outcomes in higher institutions is inconclusive, with studies reporting varied results and methodologies. Again, lack of attention to regulatory and

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governance challenges as prior research tends to overlook the impact of regulatory compliance and governance structures on audit quality and financial reporting in higher institutions. Addressing these knowledge gaps is what the current research seeks to achieve as it empirically investigates the relationship between audit quality and financial reporting in higher institutions.

Objective of the Study

The aim of this research work is to investigate the relationship between audit quality and financial reporting of higher institutions in Rivers State. The specific objectives are to:

1. Explore the effect audit independence on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the effect audit fees on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
3. Ascertain the effect audit expertise on relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
4. Investigate the effect of audit tenure on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
5. Investigate the effect audit independence on timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
6. Ascertain the effect audit fees on timeliness of financial reporting quality of higher institutions in Rivers State.

7. Assess the effect audit expertise on timeliness of financial reporting of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

8. Evaluate the effect of audit tenure on the timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

These research questions will guide this study.

1. How does audit independence influence the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
2. What is the effect audit fees on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
3. How does audit expertise influence the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
4. What is the effect of audit tenure on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
5. What is the effect audit independence on the timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
6. How does audit fees influence the timeliness of financial reporting quality of higher institutions in Rivers State?
7. What is the effect audit expertise on the timeliness of financial reporting of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
8. How does audit tenure influence the timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

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The following hypotheses will guide this study

H₀₁: Audit independence does not have significant effect on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of audit fees on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

H₀₃: There is no significant impact of audit expertise on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

H₀₄: Audit tenure does not have significant influence on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

H₀₅: There is no significant impact of audit independence on the timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

H₀₆: There is no significant influence of audit fees on the timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

H₀₇: There is no significant impact of audit expertise on the timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

H₀₈: Audit tenure does not have significant influence on the timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Concept of Audit Quality: Audit quality remains one of the most significant yet complex constructs in auditing research. Despite decades

of scholarly inquiry, there is still no universally accepted definition of audit quality because it is inherently multidimensional and cannot be directly observed. Consequently, scholars have relied on various proxies, including auditor independence, audit competence, audit fees, audit tenure, earnings quality, and the propensity of auditors to detect and report material misstatements (Francis, 2024). The conceptual foundation of audit quality is rooted in the seminal work of DeAngelo (1981), who defined audit quality as the joint probability that an auditor will both discover a material breach in a client's accounting system and report the breach. This definition highlights two fundamental dimensions of audit quality: auditor competence, which reflects the ability to detect misstatements, and auditor independence, which reflects the willingness to disclose them. DeAngelo's framework continues to underpin contemporary audit quality research and serves as the basis for most empirical investigations. Subsequent developments in the literature have expanded the concept beyond auditor competence and independence. The International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB, 2014) conceptualizes audit quality as the outcome of a comprehensive audit process involving appropriate inputs, effective audit procedures, reliable outputs, stakeholder interactions, and environmental factors. This perspective suggests that audit quality is not merely an individual auditor attribute but rather

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a function of the broader institutional and regulatory environment within which audits are conducted. Recent studies increasingly view audit quality as an ecosystem-based construct shaped by interactions among auditors, audit firms, corporate governance mechanisms, regulators, and capital market participants. According to Francis (2024), audit quality should be understood as the product of a complex auditing ecosystem in which organizational structure, regulatory oversight, professional standards, and market incentives collectively influence audit outcomes. This broader perspective aligns with contemporary quality management standards, particularly ISQM 1 and ISQM 2, which emphasise proactive quality management, risk assessment, leadership commitment, and continuous monitoring as critical determinants of audit quality. Therefore, audit quality can be conceptualized as the extent to which an audit is conducted in compliance with professional and ethical standards, enabling auditors to detect and report material misstatements while enhancing the credibility and reliability of financial reporting. Contemporary literature suggests that achieving audit quality requires the integration of auditor competence, independence, professional skepticism, effective quality management systems, and supportive institutional environments. So, audit quality should be viewed not only as an audit outcome but also as a reflection of the effectiveness of the

entire financial reporting and assurance ecosystem. This study of audit quality and financial statement quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State adopted audit independence and audit fees as proxies.

Audit independence: Auditor independence is a fundamental principle underpinning the credibility, reliability, and integrity of external auditing function. It represents the auditor's ability to perform audit engagements objectively and without being influenced by personal interests, client pressures, or other factors that may impair professional judgment. According to International Ethics Standard Board for Accountants (2024), audit independence comprises both independence of mind and independence in appearance, emphasizing the need for auditors to be free from actual and perceived conflicts of interests. Francis (2024) suggest that auditor independence extends beyond individual auditor behavior to include broader institutional, economic, and regulatory influences that shape audit outcomes.

Audit Fees: Audit fee refers to the remuneration payable to an auditor for audit services rendered. In other words, an audit fee is a fee that a company pays an external auditor in exchange for performing an audit. Furthermore, the audit fee charged is influenced by auditor dependent on the audit committee: the reputation of the auditor, auditor experience, competition in the audit market (Francis, 2024). Studies revealed that unusually high and

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unusually low audit fees may have important implications for audit quality. **Audit Expertise:** Audit expertise refers to the auditor's specialized knowledge, skills, experience, and professional judgment that enables the effective identification, assessment, and resolution of complex audit issues. Audit expertise is an essential determinant of FRQ because expert auditors possess the specialized knowledge, experience and professional judgment required to identify material misstatements, assess complex accounting estimates, and evaluate the adequacy of financial disclosures. Feliciano and Quick (2022), Dierynck et al (2024) studies show that auditor expertise contributes to improved financial reporting quality by enhancing audit effectiveness, strengthening compliance with accounting standards, and increasing the reliability of financial information provided to stakeholders.

Audit Tenure: Audit tenure refers to the number of consecutive years an audit firm or audit partner provides audit services to the same client. It reflects the duration of the auditor – client relationships and is considered an important attribute of audit quality and financial reporting quality. Longer audit tenure enables auditors to accumulate client-specific knowledge, gain a deeper understanding of business operations and internal controls, and improve the efficiency and effectiveness of audit procedures. However, excessively long tenure

may create familiarity threats that could impair auditor independence and professional skepticism (Cheynel & Zhou, 2024). The effect of audit tenure on financial reporting quality remains an empirical issue, with studies reporting both positive and negative outcomes depending on the institutional and regulatory (Asogba et al, 2024; Sadiq et al, 2023). Therefore, the relationship between audit tenure and FRQ is often viewed as a trade-off between knowledge benefits and independence risks (Cheynel & Zhou, 2024; Lee et al, 2024).

Concept of Financial Reporting Quality: Financial reporting quality (FRQ) in the public sector refers to the extent to which financial reports provide relevant, reliable, transparent, and faithfully represented information that enables stakeholders to evaluate government accountability, stewardship, and decision-making effectiveness. In public sector, financial reporting is the practice of collecting, analyzing, classifying summarizing and giving stewardship of financial activities over a period usually a year to the stakeholders (Francis, 2024; Li & Liu, 2024; Yamen & Can, 2023; Asogba et al, 2024). Jonas and Blanchet (2000), in their opinion described financial reporting as faithfulness of accounting information transmitted through financial reporting process. He further informed that the output of financial reporting is not limited to but includes disclosure of corporate transitions, details regarding selection of accounting application, policies and judgments.

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The conceptual foundation of public sector financial reporting quality is embedded in the framework developed which identifies accountability and decision usefulness as the primary objectives of government financial reporting. According to IPSASB (2023), high-quality financial reports should provide information that enables users to assess their financial position, financial performance, cash flows, service delivery capacity, and stewardship of public resources by government entities. This perspective emphasizes that financial reporting quality extends beyond compliance with accounting standards to include the usefulness of financial information for governance and accountability purposes. FRQ is grounded in the qualitative characteristics of useful financial information as articulated in conceptual accounting frameworks. Among these characteristics, completeness, neutrality, and timeliness are central to faithful representation and decision usefulness, forming core criteria through which the quality of financial reports is assessed in the public sector. Completeness refers to the extent to which financial statements include all information necessary to faithfully represent underlying economic events. It requires that all material transactions, events, and disclosures that could influence users' economic decisions are fully reported without omission. Neutrality refers to the absence of bias in the preparation and presentation of financial information. It requires that financial reports are

not influenced by intentions to achieve predetermined outcomes, thereby ensuring objective representation of economic reality. Timeliness refers to the availability of financial information to users in time to influence economic and governance decisions (IPSAB, 2023).

Theoretical Review

Agency theory provides a dominant theoretical lens for explaining the link between audit quality and financial reporting quality (FRQ) in public sector organisations, including tertiary institutions. Originating from Jensen and Meckling (1976), the theory conceptualizes organisations as a nexus of contracts in which principals delegate authority to agents. In the context of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria, principals (government, governing councils, and stakeholders) delegate resource management responsibilities to institutional managers (vice chancellors, bursars, registrars, and other administrative officers). A central assumption of agency theory is the presence of information asymmetry and divergent interests between principals and agents. Managers typically possess superior information about financial operations, while principals have limited ability to monitor day-to-day activities. This asymmetry creates incentives for opportunistic behavior such as misreporting, inefficient resource utilization, and manipulation of financial information, which ultimately undermines financial reporting

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quality. Within this framework, audit quality functions as an essential monitoring mechanism for reducing agency problems. High-quality auditing enhances financial reporting credibility by increasing the likelihood that material misstatements are detected and appropriately reported. Consistent with the audit quality model of DeAngelo (1981), audit quality is determined by both auditor competence and independence, which jointly constrain managerial opportunism and improve reporting integrity. In tertiary institutions, effective audit quality strengthens financial reporting quality by improving transparency, accountability, and compliance with financial regulations. External audits, supported by internal control systems and governance structures, reduce information asymmetry and enhance the reliability of financial statements. Prior empirical literature (Agwor & Amangala, 2020; Wobo et al, 2024; Kajola et al, 2023) in the Nigerian public sector supports this theoretical position, indicating that stronger audit mechanisms are associated with improved financial reporting outcomes and reduced reporting irregularities. Thus, agency theory suggests that financial reporting quality in tertiary institutions is largely a function of the effectiveness of audit processes in mitigating agency conflicts and enforcing accountability. Therefore, agency theory is a helpful theory that can explain the relationship between some of the study's variables, and it is important to include in the development process. The stronger the audit

quality, the higher the expected reliability, transparency, and credibility of financial statements in public universities and other tertiary institutions in Rivers State. This study therefore focuses on Agency theory which enables us to assess the extent to which the audit quality affects financial reporting of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Empirical Review

Li & Liu (2024) argue that higher audit fees can indicate a more extensive audit process, which reduces information asymmetry and aligns the interests of shareholders and management. Thus, higher fees may reflect a stronger monitoring role played by auditors. Larger audit firms are often perceived as more capable of conducting high-quality audits due to their expertise and resources. Rahman et al. (2023) found that higher audit fees are associated with improved financial reporting quality, especially in firms with complex operations. The study argues that higher audit fees reflect the auditor's effort to provide a thorough and high-quality audit, reducing the likelihood of financial misstatements. Chen et al. (2024) observed that while higher audit fees are generally associated with better reporting quality, the relationship is moderated by factors such as the firm's size and industry. The study suggests that in some cases, higher fees do not necessarily equate to better quality, particularly in smaller firms where the incremental benefit of additional audit work might be limited. Yeng and Oppoung (2024)

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studied the impact of audit independence on financial reporting quality in Sub-Saharan African stock markets. Analyzing data from 106 publicly traded companies across six stock markets from 2012 to 2021, they found that audit tenure positively influenced financial reporting quality. The size of the audit firm had a positive but insignificant effect. Importantly, audit fees were found to have a positive and notable impact on financial reporting quality. These findings highlight the crucial role of audit fees in enhancing the quality of financial reporting, particularly in emerging markets like Sub-Saharan Africa. Okoh and Audu (2023) examined how auditor independence, including audit tenure and fees, affects financial reporting quality in Nigeria's FMCG sector. Surveying audit professionals from publicly listed FMCG companies, the research showed that audit fees and non-audit services had no significant impact on financial reporting quality. However, the length of the audit tenure was found to have a notable impact on financial reporting quality. These results suggest that while audit fees may not directly influence financial reporting, factors like tenure may play a more significant role in maintaining audit quality. Pham et al. (2024) examined factors affecting the quality of audits in Vietnamese commercial banks, particularly distinguishing between Big 4 and Non-Big 4 firms. Data was collected from 226 independent auditors across 20 firms in Vietnam from April to August 2023. The research ranked key factors

influencing audit quality, including auditors' skills, the characteristics of commercial banks, time constraints, and audit procedures. They found that auditors' capabilities and the legal environment significantly impacted audit quality, while the size and reputation of the audit firm played a lesser role in affecting financial reporting quality. Sadiq et al (2023) impact of audit fees on financial reporting quality listed non-financial services firms. in Nigeria, which their study period 2011-2021 data collected from annual reports of 30 listed non-financial services firms and Descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis. The results show audit fees do not have a direct effect on financial reporting quality. These studies highlight the complex relationship between audit fees and financial reporting quality.

Methodology

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design to investigate the link between audit quality and financial statement quality among tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The survey design was considered appropriate because it facilitates the collection of quantitative data from respondents at a single point in time and enables the investigation of associations between the study variables. The population of the study comprised fifteen (15) public and private tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. These institutions consisted of the study population due to their responsibility for preparing financial statements and

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implementing audit processes aimed at ensuring accountability, transparency, and financial reporting quality. A census sampling technique was adopted for this study because the target population was relatively small and manageable. Consequently, all members of the population were included in the study, eliminating sampling bias and ensuring comprehensive coverage of the population. The use of census sampling is appropriate when researchers seek to collect information from every unit within the population rather than selecting a representative subset of the population. This approach minimizes sampling error and improves the generalizability of findings to the population under study (Appah, 2020). Respondents were drawn from key departments directly involved in financial reporting and auditing activities, including bursary units, internal audit units, institutional management, and budgeting and planning unit. Personnel occupying supervisory and managerial positions were purposively selected due to their familiarity with audit procedures and financial reporting practices. The study relied on primary data collected through the administration of a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was adapted from previous studies on audit quality and modified to suit the context of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A elicited demographic information of respondents, while Section B contained items measuring the

dimensions of audit quality. Audit quality was measured using audit independence and audit fees. Financial statements quality was measured using dimensions such as completeness, relevance and timelines. Responses were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4) and strongly agree (5). The validity of the instrument was established through face and content validity procedures. Copies of the questionnaire were reviewed by experts in accounting, auditing, and research methods to determine the relevance, clarity, and adequacy of the items in measuring the study constructs. Their observations and recommendations informed the modification and refinement of the instrument before final administration. Construct validity was further assessed using exploratory factor analysis. Factor loadings were examined to ensure that questionnaire items adequately measured their respective constructs. The reliability of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. A minimum threshold of 0.70 was adopted as the benchmark for acceptable reliability. The results indicate that all study constructs exceeded the recommended threshold, demonstrating satisfactory internal consistency and reliability of the measurement scales. Copies of the questionnaire were administered directly to respondents in the twelve (12) selected tertiary institutions. The researchers employed a combination of personal visits and institutional

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobowei (Ph.D., FCA)

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contacts to facilitate questionnaire distribution and retrieval. Respondents were given sufficient time to complete the instrument after which completed copies were collected for analysis. Data collected from the field was coded and analyzed using statistical software and the analysis was conducted at three levels of univariate analysis, bivariate analysis and multivariate analysis. The multiple regression was guided by a linear model below:

$$RFRQ = \beta_0 + \beta_1AUDI + \beta_2AUFE + \beta_3AUEx + \beta_4AUTE + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$TFRQ = \beta_0 + \beta_1AUDI + \beta_2AUFE + \beta_3AUEx + \beta_4AUTE + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

AUDI = Audit Independence, AUFE = Audit Fee, AUEx = Audit Expertise, AUTE = Audit Tenure, RFRQ = Relevance of Financial Reporting Quality and TFRQ = Timeliness of Financial Reporting Quality. $\beta_0 - \beta_4$ represent the regression coefficient, while ε represents the

error term. According to Appah (2020), the interpretation of correlation (r) parameters is 0.8 – 1.0 = very strong relationship, 0.6 – 0.79 = strong relationship, 0.4 – 0.59 = moderate relationship, 0.2 – 0.39 = weak relationship; and 0.0 – 0.19 = very weak or no relationship. The study utilised a 5% level of significance; hence we conclude that the coefficient is significantly different from zero at the 5% level if the p-values is less than or equal to 0.05. If it is greater than 0.05 then we cannot reject the null hypothesis that the coefficient is zero at our 5% significance level.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The primary data was collected from respondents using the questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed and later retrieved by the respondents. The primary data collected was then subjected to analysis. From the sample, 380 copies of the questionnaire were distributed.

Table 1 Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient of Reliability

Name	Reliability (Cronbach’s Alpha)	Reliability Level
Audit Independence on Relevance	0.715	Accepted
Audit Independence on Timeliness	0.740	Accepted
Audit Fees on Relevance	0.726	Accepted
Audit Fees on Timeliness	0.726	Accepted
Audit Expertise on Relevance	0.733	Accepted
Audit Expertise on Timeliness	0.771	Accepted

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobwei (Ph.D., FCA)

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Audit Tenure on Relevance	0.713	Accepted
Audit Tenure on Timeliness	0.721	Accepted

Source: E- view output (2026)

All the variables listed in Table 1 have Cronbach's Alpha values that are either above or near the acceptable threshold of 0.7, suggesting that the instruments used to measure audit independence, audit fees, audit expertise and

audit tenure on various factors (Relevance and timeliness on financial reporting) have acceptable to good internal consistency. This indicates that the items within each category are reliably measuring the same underlying construct.

Table 2: Questionnaire Distribution

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Number Retrieved	232	77.3	77.3	77.3
Number not retrieved	57	19.0	19.0	96.3
Number not properly filed	11	3.7	3.7	100.0
Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 shows the distribution and collection of questionnaires sent to the respondents. It was shown that 300 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, representing 100%. 232 questionnaires representing 77.3% were correctly filled and successfully retrieved from the

respondents; however, 57 questionnaires representing 19.0% were not retrieved, and 11 questionnaires representing 3.7% were not properly filed. Consequently, only 232 questionnaires representing 77.3% were used for data analysis.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Error	Std. Deviation	Variance
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
Q1	232	2.00	5.00	3.9184	.08903	.88135	.777
Q2	232	1.00	5.00	3.7755	.08145	.80630	.650
Q3	232	2.00	5.00	3.6735	.08915	.88254	.779
Q4	232	2.00	5.00	3.7143	.09400	.93058	.866
Q5	232	1.00	5.00	3.5204	.10177	1.00749	1.015

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobwei (Ph.D., FCA)

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Q6	232	2.00	5.00	3.5204	.10280	1.01767	1.036
Q7	232	1.00	5.00	3.6735	.09487	.93913	.882
Q8	232	2.00	5.00	3.8673	.09016	.89256	.797
Q9	232	2.00	5.00	3.7143	.09058	.89673	.804
Q10	232	2.00	5.00	3.7245	.08797	.87084	.758
Q11	232	2.00	5.00	3.4898	.09539	.94427	.892
Q12	232	2.00	5.00	3.6122	.10219	1.01161	1.023
Q13	232	1.00	5.00	3.4184	.10452	1.03469	1.071
Q14	232	1.00	5.00	3.4694	.10277	1.01742	1.035
Q15	232	1.00	5.00	3.3878	.10916	1.08059	1.168
Q16	232	1.00	5.00	3.4592	.10871	1.07616	1.158
Q17	232	1.00	5.00	3.3469	.11793	1.16745	1.363
Q18	232	1.00	5.00	3.2755	.12710	1.25822	1.583
Q19	232	1.00	5.00	3.2449	.12054	1.19329	1.424
Q20	232	1.00	5.00	3.3265	.12289	1.21651	1.480
Q21	232	1.00	5.00	3.3776	.10904	1.07947	1.165
Q22	232	1.00	5.00	3.3163	.10619	1.05123	1.105
Q23	232	1.00	5.00	3.5612	.10466	1.03611	1.074
Q24	232	1.00	5.00	3.2551	.13319	1.31847	1.738
Q25	232	1.00	5.00	3.1633	.13737	1.35991	1.849
Q26	232	1.00	5.00	3.6327	.12426	1.23010	1.513
Q27	232	1.00	5.00	3.3673	.13482	1.33461	1.781
Q28	232	1.00	5.00	3.5408	.10967	1.08569	1.179
Q29	232	1.00	5.00	3.1837	.12839	1.27098	1.615
Q30	232	1.00	5.00	3.5510	.11615	1.14983	1.322
Q31	232	1.00	5.00	3.4184	.10750	1.06416	1.132
Q32	232	1.00	5.00	3.5204	.08968	.88783	.788
Valid (listwise)	N232						

Source: E- view output (2026)

The descriptive statistics reflect a generally positive perception of audit quality and financial

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobwei (Ph.D., FCA)

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reporting in tertiary institutions, with mean scores consistently indicating agreement or neutrality leaning towards agreement (ranging from 3.16 to 3.92). Audit independence received high ratings, emphasizing its significant role in ensuring the relevance and timeliness of financial reporting, with relatively low variability in responses. Similarly, the audit fees were positively regarded for their contributions to unbiased and complete financial reporting, with most respondents agreeing on their importance, though views on its role in ensuring timeliness

showed slightly more variability. Audit expertise was also viewed positively, with respondents acknowledging their influence on the thoroughness of financial reporting, although opinions were more divided regarding their effect on timeliness. General feedback highlighted confidence in the auditing process and its ability to enhance the quality of financial reports, reinforcing the overall positive sentiment toward audit practices in the institutions evaluated.

Table 4 Correlation Coefficients and Significance Levels

Hypotheses	Relevance		Timeliness	
	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. Level	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. Level
Audit Independence	0.674	0.000	0.725	0.000
Audit Fee	0.670	0.000	0.654	0.000
Audit Expertise	0.620	0.001	0.685	0.000
Audit Tenure	0.606	0.000	0.725	0.000

Source: E- view output (2026)

The Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) analysis shows the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Table 4 shows a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.674$, $P = 0.000$) between audit independence and relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.670$, $P = 0.000$) between audit fees and relevance of

financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.620$, $P = 0.0001$) between audit expertise and relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; and a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.606$, $P = 0.000$) between audit tenure and relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study further revealed a strong and

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobwei (Ph.D., FCA)

positive relationship ($r = 0.725$, $P = 0.000$) between audit independence and timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.654$, $P = 0.000$) between audit fees and timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.685$, $P = 0.000$) between audit expertise and timeliness of

financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; and a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.725$, $P = 0.000$) between audit tenure and timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings therefore revealed a strong and positive relationship between audit quality and the FRQ of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis Model One

Dependent Variable: RFRQ

Method: Least Squares

Date: 06/10/26 Time: 18:15

Sample(adjusted): 1 232

Included observations: 232 after adjusting endpoints

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.275444	2.256856	1.451330	0.1488
AUID	0.285935	0.095662	2.989017	0.0327
AUFE	0.284753	0.148523	2.847532	0.0345
AUEX	0.249495	0.106627	2.339885	0.0254
AUTE	0.234756	0.112637	2.126453	0.0264
R-squared	0.627842	Mean dependent var		12.99346
Adjusted R-squared	0.547163	S.D. dependent var		3.098167
S.E. of regression	2.718266	Akaike info criterion		4.997962
Sum squared resid	1234.711	Schwarz criterion		5.116803
Log likelihood	-3126.3441	F-statistic		5.837465

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Durbin-Watson stat	2.364372	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000100
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Source: e-view output

Table 5 shows the multiple regression analysis for the impact of audit quality on the relevance of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The regression analysis indicated a significantly positive ($0.0327 < 0.05$) between audit independence (AUID) and relevance of financial reporting quality (RFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; a significantly positive ($0.0345 < 0.05$) between audit fee (AUFE) and relevance of financial reporting quality (RFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; a significantly positive ($0.0254 < 0.05$) between audit expertise (AUEX) and relevance of financial reporting quality (RFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State,

Nigeria; and a significantly positive ($0.0264 < 0.05$) between audit tenure (AUTE) and relevance of financial reporting quality (RFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The F-statistics and its probability shows that the regression equation is well formulated explaining that the relationship between the audit quality of AUID, AUFE, AUEX and AUTE on relevance of financial reporting quality (RFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. are significant (F-stat = 5.837465; F-pro. = 0.000100). Therefore, the findings suggested a positive and significant relationship between audit quality and the relevance of financial reporting quality (RFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis Model Two

Dependent Variable: TFRQ

Method: Least Squares

Date: 06/10/26 Time: 1923

Sample(adjusted): 1 232

Included observations: 232 after adjusting endpoints

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.275444	2.256856	1.451330	0.1488
AUID	0.382834	0.182347	2.394851	0.0226
AUFE	0.238474	0.283415	2.398345	0.0254
AUEX	0.374625	0.273547	2.362535	0.0253

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobwei (Ph.D., FCA)

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AUTE	0.275632	0.123481	2.384517	0.0352
R-squared	0.648625	Mean dependent var		12.99346
Adjusted R-squared	0.537534	S.D. dependent var		3.098167
S.E. of regression	2.718266	Akaike info criterion		4.997962
Sum squared resid	1234.711	Schwarz criterion		5.116803
Log likelihood	-3126.3441	F-statistic		5.837465
Durbin-Watson stat	2.364372	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000100

Source: e-view output

Table 6 shows the multiple regression analysis for the impact of audit quality on the timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The regression analysis indicated a significantly positive ($0.0226 < 0.05$) between audit independence (AUID) and timeliness of financial reporting quality (TFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; a significantly positive ($0.0254 < 0.05$) between audit fee (AUFE) and timeliness of financial reporting quality (TFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; a significantly positive ($0.0253 < 0.05$) between audit expertise (AUEX) and relevance of financial reporting quality (TFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria; and a significantly positive ($0.0352 < 0.05$) between

audit tenure (AUTE) and relevance of financial reporting quality (TFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The F-statistics and its probability shows that the regression equation is well formulated explaining that the relationship between the audit quality of AUID, AUFE, AUEX and AUTE on timeliness of financial reporting quality (TFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. are significant (F-stat = 5.837465; F-pro. = 0.000100). Therefore, the findings suggested a positive and significant relationship between audit quality and the timeliness of financial reporting quality (TFRQ) of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Audit Independence and Financial Reporting Quality: The study found a positive and significant relationship between audit

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobowei (Ph.D., FCA)

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independence and financial reporting quality, particularly in terms of relevance and timeliness, among tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. This finding suggests that as auditors become more independent in the execution of their responsibilities, the quality of financial reports produced by tertiary institutions improves significantly. Specifically, independent auditors are better positioned to provide objective assessments of financial records, thereby enhancing the usefulness, credibility, and promptness of financial information for decision-making. The finding that audit independence enhances the relevance of financial reports implies that independent auditors facilitate the disclosure of financial information capable of influencing stakeholders' economic and administrative decisions. Furthermore, the significant association between audit independence and timeliness indicates that independent auditors contribute to the prompt completion of audit engagements and the early release of financial reports. The result is consistent with prior empirical evidence. Studies of Yeng and Oppong (2024), Okegbe et al (2019), Yikarebogha (2025), Okoh and Audu (2024), and Sawaya et al (2025), consistently show that auditor independence improves audit quality, reporting credibility, reliability, timeliness, and overall financial reporting quality. These studies collectively suggest that independent auditors provide objective oversight, reduce information asymmetry, constrain managerial opportunism, and ensure compliance with accounting

standards, thereby enhancing the quality of financial reports available to stakeholders. In the context of tertiary institutions, the significance of audit independence may be even more pronounced because these institutions manage public funds and are accountable to multiple stakeholders. Consequently, independent auditors can provide unbiased assurance regarding the stewardship of institutional resources, thereby enhancing public trust and institutional legitimacy.

Audit Fees and Financial Reporting Quality: The study found audit fees have a positive and statistically significant relationship with financial reporting quality, particularly in terms of relevance and timeliness, among tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. This finding implies that institutions that incur higher audit fees tend to produce financial reports that are more useful for decision-making and are released in a timely manner. The result suggests that higher audit fees may reflect greater audit effort, enhanced auditor expertise, and more comprehensive audit procedures, which collectively contribute to improved financial reporting quality. The result corroborates the findings of Asogba et al (2024), who reported that audit fees significantly improve financial reporting quality among quoted non-financial firms in Nigeria. The authors argue that higher audit fees enable auditors to devote greater effort and professional diligence to audit engagements, thereby improving the reliability and usefulness of

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobwei (Ph.D., FCA)

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financial statements. Similarly, Hartaty and Dianawati (2024), in their analysis of audit fees and audit quality, found a significant positive link between audit fees and audit quality. Their study concluded that adequate audit compensation enhances audit effectiveness and improves the credibility of financial reporting. The finding also aligns with the study of Li and Liu (2024), who observed that normal audit fees are positively linked with financial reporting quality because they reflect the resources and effort required to perform a comprehensive audit. Furthermore, Saifudin and Januarti (2023) reported that organizations that provide adequate audit remuneration benefit from higher audit quality and more credible financial reporting outcome. The positive association observed in this study may also be attributed to the capacity for adequately funded audit engagements to improve reporting timeliness. Auditors with sufficient resources are better positioned to complete audit assignments efficiently, reducing delays in the publication of financial statements. Therefore, the finding demonstrates that investment in quality audit services contributes significantly to improving the relevance and timeliness of financial reporting among tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The result underscores the relevance of providing adequate audit resources as a means of strengthening transparency, accountability, and financial governance within tertiary education institutions.

Audit Expertise and Financial Reporting

Quality: The study found a positive and significant relationship between audit expertise and financial reporting quality, particularly in terms of relevance and timeliness, among tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The positive association suggests that as the level of audit expertise increases within tertiary institutions, the quality of financial reports improves significantly. Specifically, professionally competent auditors are more capable of identifying accounting errors, ensuring compliance with applicable accounting standards, strengthening internal controls, and promoting accurate disclosure practices. Recent studies continue to affirm that auditor expertise – particularly industry specialization and technical competence – enhances audit quality, which in turn improves financial reporting outcomes. For instance, Muchlish and Istak (2024) found that auditor industry specialization significantly reduces audit report lag in listed firms. Their study demonstrates that specialized auditors possess deeper knowledge of clients' operations and industry-specific accounting risks, enabling them to plan audits more efficiently and complete audit procedures faster. Similarly, Yahaya and Bello (2025) found that hiring external auditors with industry expertise significantly improves financial reporting quality among Nigerian listed firms. Their study demonstrates that auditor specialization enhances accrual quality, reduces reporting distortions, and strengthens compliance with

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobwei (Ph.D., FCA)

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financial reporting standards. Furthermore, Dattijo and Inowa (2025) show that audit expertise significantly enhances financial reporting quality. Their findings indicate that expert auditors improve the credibility of financial statements by reducing errors and strengthening quality, thereby increasing the usefulness of financial reports for stakeholders. Bello (2026) provides robust evidence that audit expertise is significantly linked with reduced audit lag in Nigerian firms. Therefore, the statistically significant positive link observed in this study implies that strengthening audit expertise within tertiary institutions can serve as an effective mechanism for improving the relevance and timeliness of financial reports. Management and governing councils of tertiary institutions should prioritize the recruitment, training, and continuous professional development of auditors to enhance financial reporting quality and institutional accountability.

Audit Tenure and Financial Reporting Quality: The study found a positive and significant relationship between audit tenure and financial reporting quality, particularly in terms of relevance and timeliness, among tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The finding suggests that longer auditor-client connection enhance auditors' understanding of institutional systems, improve audit efficiency, and strengthen the credibility and usefulness of financial reports. Recent empirical evidence from Egypt and other emerging markets

confirms that audit tenure significantly influences audit report lag, a widely accepted proxy for financial reporting timeliness. Abouelela et al (2025) found that audit tenure significantly affects audit report lag in Egyptian listed firms, indicating that longer auditor engagement improves audit efficiency through accumulated client-specific knowledge. Similarly, Farumi et al (2023) provide evidence that audit tenure significantly affects audit report lag in Indonesian firms. Similarly, Sadiq et al (2023) reported that audit tenure positively influences financial reporting quality because auditors with adequate experience are better positioned to ensure compliance with accounting standards and reporting regulations. This implies that auditors who have worked with an institution for several years are more familiar with their accounting processes and documentation requirements, thereby reducing the time required to conduct audit procedures and finalise audit reports. The finding is also consistent with Gbadebo (2025), who found that audit related characteristics significantly improve the timeliness of financial reporting by reducing audit delays and facilitating prompt issuance of financial statements. The findings demonstrate that audit tenure plays an important role in enhancing the quality of financial reporting in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Conclusion, Policy Implications, Limitations and Future Research

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobowei (Ph.D., FCA)

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The empirical findings of this study provide robust evidence that audit independence, audit fees, audit expertise, and audit tenure exert a positive and statistically significant influence on the relevance and timeliness of financial reporting quality in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. Collectively, these results reinforce the theoretical proposition that audit quality attributes constitute critical governance mechanisms that enhance the credibility, usefulness, and temporal responsiveness of financial reporting in public sector educational institutions. Specifically, the significance of audit independence confirms that objective and unbiased audit engagement remains fundamental to ensuring faithful representation of financial statements in environments characterized by public accountability pressures and complex funding structures, independence strengthens professional skepticism and mitigates managerial discretion, thereby improving both the reliability and decision-usefulness of reported financial information. The positive effect of audit fees suggests that audit effort intensity is economically determined with adequate remuneration enabling auditors to allocate sufficient time, technical resources, and specialized procedures necessary for high-quality audit execution. Furthermore, the statistical significance of audit expertise underscores the relevance of specialized knowledge and professional competence in interpreting complex institutional transactions typically of tertiary institutions financial

systems. Expertise enhances auditors' ability to detect misstatements, apply appropriate accounting standards, and ensure that financial reports meet both regulatory and stakeholder expectations in terms of clarity and timeliness. Similarly, the positive connection between audit tenure and FRQ indicates that continuity in auditor engagement can enhance institutional knowledge accumulation, improve audit efficiency, and strengthen reporting timeliness. Generally, the study demonstrates that strengthening audit governance structures significantly enhances both the relevance and timeliness dimensions of financial reporting quality in tertiary institutions.

The finding that audit independence, audit fees, audit expertise and audit tenure have a positive and statistically significant connection with the relevance and timeliness of financial reporting quality of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria, carries important policy implications for institutional governance, regulatory oversight, and public sector accountability. First, governing councils and management of tertiary institutions should establish mechanisms that minimize undue influence on auditors, including independent appointment procedures, clear reporting lines and strict compliance with professional ethical standards. Second, policymakers should ensure that tertiary institutions allocate sufficient budgetary resources for audit functions and avoid practices that prioritize cost minimization over audit quality. Third, institutional management and

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobwei (Ph.D., FCA)

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regulatory agencies should prioritize the recruitment and retention of professionally qualified auditors with specialized knowledge of public sector accounting and tertiary education financial systems. Fourth, policymakers should establish balanced auditor rotation policies that preserve the benefits of accumulated expertise while mitigating potential familiarity threats.

Despite its contribution to the literature on audit quality and FRQ in tertiary institutions, this study is subject to several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, the study was geographically limited to tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. While the findings provide valuable insights into the connection between audit quality attributes and FRQ within this context, the results may not be fully generalizable to tertiary institutions in other states or countries with different regulatory, institutional, and governance environments. Second, the study focused exclusively on four dimensions of AQ of audit independence, audit fees, audit expertise and audit tenure. Although these variables were found to statistically influence FRQ, other potentially important determinants, such as audit committee effectiveness, internal control quality, auditor reputation, institutional governance structures, and technological adoption, were not examined. Third, the study adopted a cross-sectional research design, which captures associations at a specific point in time. Consequently, the study design limits the ability to establish long-term causal effects and may not

fully reflect changes in audit practices and FRQ over time. Fourth, the study relied on responses obtained from participants within tertiary institutions. As with survey-based studies, there is a possibility of response bias arising from subjective perceptions, social desirability tendencies, or incomplete disclosure of information by respondents.

Based on the limitations identified, several avenues for future research are recommended: First, future studies should extend the scope of investigation to tertiary institutions across multiple states in Nigeria or undertake cross-country comparisons to enhance the generalizability of findings and provide broader evidence on audit quality and financial reporting quality in higher educational institutions. Second, future researchers should examine additional dimensions of audit quality and corporate governance, including audit committee characteristics, internal audit effectiveness, auditor reputation, auditor specialization, board oversight, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of factors influencing FRQ. Third, longitudinal studies are recommended to investigate how changes in audit quality attributes influence FRQ over time. Such studies provide stronger evidence regarding causal links and sustainability of observed effects. Fourth, future research could explore the moderating role of institutional governance, regulatory compliance, organizational culture, and information technology infrastructure in the link between

Eburunobi Emmanuel Odinakachi (Ph.D.) and Appah, Ebimobwei (Ph.D., FCA)

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audit quality and FRQ. Fifth, researchers may expand the assessment of financial reporting quality by incorporating additional qualitative characteristics such as faithful representation, comparability, understandability, and verifiability, thereby providing a more holistic

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evaluation of reporting quality. Finally, future research may employ mixed method approaches that combine quantitative analysis and qualitative interviews involving auditors, regulators, governing council members, and institutional administrators.

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